

A rapid and novel method for the determination of uranium in black shales using LED based fluorometer

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Abstract : A simple, rapid and efficient method for extraction of uranium using ammonium peroxodisulphate in black shales and phosphorites samples from Dehradun area and its determination using LED based fluorimeter was developed. The effect of time, concentration of peroxodisulphate, amount of sample taken was investigated. Uranium was determined in 0.2 g sample using 20% ammonium peroxodisulphate and heating for 2 h. The accuracy of the proposed method is checked by analyzing geological samples of black shales and phosphorites from Dehradun area and the results so obtained were compared favourably with those obtained from the pellet fluorimetry method. The accuracy and reproducibility of the method are fairly good with RSD ranging from 3 to 5% depend upon the concentration of uranium.

Keywords : Fluorimetry, LED based fluorimeter, uranium, black shales, phosphorites, Dehradun, ammonium peroxodisulphate, extraction.

Introduction

Shale contains an average of a few parts per million (3 to 4 ppm) uranium. All black shales contain more uranium than the average sedimentary rock, but to be classified as uraniferous black shale it must contain more than 50 ppm U_3O_8 (Swanson, 1961). Uraniferous black shales, which are of marine origin, have high (>2%) sapropelic organic carbon (Bell, 1979). Uranium content increases with increase in organic matter. Uranium occurs as adsorbed material in organic or phosphatic molecules or absorbed by clays. No uranium minerals have been identified from these sources. Uranium in black shales is in reduced state, due to the reduced environment created by organic matter present in black shales. Besides uranium, they contain small quantities of other metals such as Mn, Ti, V, Cu, Cr, Mo, P and REE.

Uranium is determined by many methods depending on its concentration, viz. fluorimetry, spectrophotometry, volumetry and gravimetry. It is also determined by non-destructive method like X-ray fluorescence, beta-gammaradiometry, neutron activation etc.¹⁻³. Fluorimetric determination of uranium is very popular due to its high sensitivity and specificity⁴⁻⁶ and it is widely used for the determination of uranium in a variety of geological as well as nuclear materials samples. Majority of reported

works deals with the determination of uranium in igneous rocks after selective separation of uranium because many elements quench fluorescence. Laser induced fluorimetry (LIF) in aqueous medium is much more sensitive than optical fluorimetry in solid phase and is widely used for the determination of uranium directly in geological samples and also after separation of uranium⁷. Various oxidising agents had been used for the determination of uranium such as HNO_3 , H_2O_2 , $K_2Cr_2O_7$ etc. Ammonium peroxodisulphate also being strong oxidising agent was tried for the determination of uranium in black shales.

Direct laser fluorimetric determination of ultra and trace level uranium in geological samples have the following limitations¹: (1) presence of high quantity of iron, manganese and other interfering elements causes serious quenching effect, so the standard addition method which is normally adapted to overcome the interference to certain extent also fails to give accurate results; (2) preparation of sample solution in small volumes (10 to 25 ml) using relatively lower acid concentrations (higher acid concentration quenches the fluorescence of uranium) and (3) limitation in taking the entire sample for analysis which improve the determination limit considerably. So a selective separation and pre-concentration of uranium are required in complex matrices⁸.

The present method deals with extraction of uranium from the black shale and phosphorites samples using ammonium peroxodisulphate followed by its determination using LED based fluorimeter. As the sample was diluted from 0.1 to 25 ml and fluorescence enhancing buffer was used, the effect of quenchers was avoided. U(IV) in the black shales is oxidized by the [O] from ammonium peroxodisulphate.

Reaction mechanism :

or

This oxygen is required for the oxidation of uranium.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

The proposed method was studied using Quantalase LED based fluorimeter. Pellet fluorimetry was carried out using ECIL made pellet fluorimeter.

Reagents :

All reagents and standards were prepared from analytical grade and spec-pure chemicals. Double distilled water was used for all subsequent dilutions wherever required. Uranium standard stock solution of (1 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving 0.2948 g U_3O_8 in a minimum volume of nitric acid and made to 250 ml final volume. The respective individual working calibration standards were prepared from stock solutions by suitable dilutions.

Preparation of buffer :

250 g of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate was dissolved in 500 ml of water containing 60 ml of phosphoric acid. This buffer solution was used in the determination of uranium by LED based fluorimeters.

Procedure :

0.2 to 0.5 g of sample was placed in a 100 ml beaker. 50 ml of 20% ammonium peroxodisulphate solution was added, covered with watch glass and was heated on a hot plate upto 150 °C for 2 h. The solution was filtered and the residue was discarded. The filtrate was made upto 50 ml and is ready for determination of uranium. 0.1 ml of sample solution was taken in a 25 ml flask. 10 ml of fluorescence enhancing buffer was added and made upto 25 ml. The LED based fluorimeter was calibrated using uranium standards from 1 to 20 ppb and uranium was determined in the samples by the instrument.

Results and discussion

Extraction conditions :

(A) Effect of concentration of ammonium peroxodisulphate :

Extraction of uranium from black shale samples using different concentrations of ammonium peroxodisulphate was studied. Best results were obtained at 20% ammonium peroxodisulphate.

(B) Effect of amount of sample taken :

In order to investigate the effect of amount of sample, 0.1 to 0.5 g sample was taken and extraction of uranium was studied. It was found that 0.2 g of sample gave best recovery.

(C) Effect of extraction time :

In order to investigate the dependence of extraction efficiency on time of extraction, 1/2 h to 3 h heating at 150 °C was studied. Best results were obtained at 2 h heating.

The overall effect of these parameters is tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of weight of the sample, concentration of ammonium peroxodisulphate and time of extraction on the recovery of uranium

	1/2 h		1 h		2 h		3 h	
	10% APOD	20% APOD	10% APOD	20% APOD	10% APOD	20% APOD	10% APOD	20% APOD
	% U_3O_8							
0.1 g	0.038	0.045	0.044	0.047	0.047	0.047	0.050	0.044
0.2 g	0.037	0.041	0.048	0.048	0.049	0.054	0.053	0.052
0.5 g	0.035	0.046	0.049	0.053	0.054	0.047	0.050	0.041

APOD - Ammonium peroxodisulphate.

Table 2. Comparison of results obtained with the proposed method and with that of the pellet fluorimetry method for different geological samples

Sample	%U ₃ O ₈ (by LED based fluorimeter)	%U ₃ O ₈ (by pellet fluorimeter)	Sample	%U ₃ O ₈ (by LED based fluorimeter)	%U ₃ O ₈ (by pellet fluorimeter)
AMD-1	0.0001	<0.001	AMD-12	0.059	0.064
AMD-2	0.0003	<0.001	AMD-13	0.078	0.082
AMD-3	0.0004	<0.001	AMD-14	0.016	0.016
AMD-4	0.010	0.008	AMD-15	0.076	0.078
AMD-5	0.062	0.068	AMD-16	0.058	0.057
AMD-6	0.052	0.054	AMD-17	0.010	0.008
AMD-7	0.045	0.043	AMD-18	0.541	0.503
AMD-8	0.062	0.060	AMD-19	0.005	0.005
AMD-9	0.064	0.070	AMD-20	0.004	0.005
AMD-10	0.096	0.095	AMD-21	0.173	0.170
AMD-11	0.021	0.024	AMD-22	0.490	0.503

Validation of proposed method :

The proposed method was validated by the determination of uranium in variety of black shale samples received from Dehradun area by comparing the values with conventional pellet fluorimetry and the results were found in good agreement. The average concentration range of uranium in these samples were 30 to 80 ppm. The values obtained by pellet fluorimetry matched the values obtained by proposed method. The present method is being tried on other uranium mineralisation too.

Conclusion

The proposed method offers an effective alternate method of extraction and determination of uranium in black shale and phosphorites samples of Dehradun area using LED based fluorimetry. Various black shale samples from Dehradun area were analysed and compared with conventional pellet fluorimetric method (Table 2). The method is rapid, selective, precise and accurate for black shales. Following the recommended procedure, determination limit of 1 µg/g of uranium with a RSD of ±10% has been achieved for the analysis of black shales. The

method also provides the freedom from hazardous acids, salting out agents, platinum wares, high temperature fusions and fluxes as used in conventional procedure.

References

1. "Analytical Chemistry of Uranium", Compiled by P. N. Palei, Translated by N. Kaner, Ann Arbor, London, 1970.
2. H. Onishi, "Photometric Determination of Trace of Metals, Individual Metals Magnesium to Zirconium", 4th ed., Part-IIB, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1989.
3. S. Vishwanathan, "Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometry in Exploration and Research for Atomic Minerals", 1989, 2, 247.
4. F. S. Grimaldi, I. May, M. H. Fletcher and J. Titcomb, *U.S. Geological Survey Bulletin*, 1954, 1006, 3.
5. H. Onishi, "Photometric Determination of Trace of Metals, Individual Metals Magnesium to Zirconium", 6th ed., John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1989, Chap. 44, 608.
6. G. R. Price, R. J. Ferretti and S. Schwartz, "Atomic Energy Commission Department AECD-2282", International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, 1945.
7. A. Premadas and P. K. Srivastava, *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry*, 1999, 242, 23.
8. A. Premadas and G. Saravankumar, *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry*, 2005, 266, 95.

